

Physico-chemical behaviour on molecular interactions of cationic surfactant with block copolymers at different temperature

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Abstract : The interaction of dodecyltrimethylammonium chloride (DTAC) with poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO), poly(propylene oxide) (PPO) and poly(butylene oxide) (PBO) was studied by ultrasonic velocity measurements at 303 K and 323 K. Using the measured values of ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity, the other related thermodynamic parameters such as adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length, internal pressure and acoustic impedance have been evaluated. These parameters have been utilized to study the strong solute-solvent interactions in these systems. A fairly good to excellent correlation between a given parameter and concentration is observed at all temperatures and solvent systems studied. The critical micellar concentration (CMC) is formed at 1.2 mM concentration in these systems. Linear or nonlinear increase or decrease in acoustical parameters with specific concentration and temperature indicate the existence of strong molecular interactions.

Keywords : Dodecyltrimethylammonium chloride, ultrasonic velocity, viscosity, acoustical parameters.

Introduction

Physicochemical investigations of surfactant-polymer system in aqueous solutions provide a lot of information about their microscopic structure. Surfactant-polymer complexes make the multi component system control the aggregation behavior in a much better manner compared to individual pure polymer or surfactant systems. The find use in a wide range of applications such as templates development of nanoscale materials in drug delivery, pharmaceutical, petroleum and detergent formulation^{1,2}.

Many industrial formulations such as detergents, paints, foodstuff and cosmetics contain both surfactant and block copolymers their mutual interaction govern many properties in these materials. Polymer-surfactant complexes are used for instance in laundry detergents, tertiary oil recovery and in a number of cosmetic, household products and drug delivery systems. The presence of polymers in aqueous solutions of surfactant causes changes in the physical properties of the micelle aggregates formed by the surfactant. The mixed micelle formation in copolymer-surfactant systems were reported³⁻⁷. The system dodecyltrimethylammonium chloride (DTAC) with

poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO), poly(propylene oxide) (PPO) and poly(butylene oxide) (PBO) has been blended and analyzed from the conventional methods. Surfactant-polymer interactions involve various modes of association like dipole-dipole or ion-ion forces.

In aqueous surfactant-polymer solutions, polymer readily forms aggregates with a surfactant above a particular surfactant concentration, known as the Critical Association Concentration (CAC). The CAC for a polymer-surfactant system is often very much lower than the Critical Micellar Concentration (CMC) of the surfactant. The properties of micelles depend upon parameters like temperature, pressure, concentration, the chemical nature of the surfactant etc.

Experimental

Dodecyltrimethylammonium chloride (Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd.) and poly(ethylene oxide), poly(butylene oxide), poly(propylene oxide) (AR grade, Merck India Ltd., India) were used for this work. The stock solutions (0.3 mM) of 1 M concentration were prepared by weighing the DTAC on a digital balance with an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times$

10⁻⁵ kg. Solutions of PEO, PBO and PPO were made on the molality concentration scale.

Stock solutions of surfactant and the blends of DTAC/PEO, DTAC/PPO and DTAC/PBO were prepared in various soluble concentrations ranging from 0.3 to 1.2 (mM) in order to determine the CMC of DTAC (0.3 mM). Viscosity measurements at 303 K and 323 K were made using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer with the flow time of 98 s for distilled water. The total weight of the two components in the solution was always maintained at 1 g/dL. The ultrasonic velocity measurements were performed by an ultrasonic interferometric (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) technique⁸. The temperatures were maintained at 303 K and 323 K by circulating water from a thermostat, with a thermal stability of ±0.05 °C, through the double-walled jacket of the ultrasonic experimental cell. The experimental frequency was 2 MHz, and the velocity measurements were accurate to better than ±0.5%. The densities of the solutions were measured at 303 K and 323 K by specific gravity bottle.

Results and discussion

The values of ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity are measured for aqueous solutions of the surfactant

in presence of added PEO, PBO and PPO having different concentrations at 303 K and 323 K temperature. The thermodynamic parameters such as adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length, internal pressure and acoustic impedance at different concentration of surfactant with PEO, PPO and PBO at CMC values are presented in Tables 1 to 3.

From the Tables (1 to 3), it is found that ultrasonic velocity for aqueous solutions of DTAC (Stock solutions 0.3 mM)/(PEO, PPO and PBO) increases from 0.3 to 0.9 mM concentration and then decreases. The critical micellar concentration (CMC) is formed at 1.2 mM concentration for aqueous DTAC/PEO, DTAC/PPO and DTAC/PBO solutions.

The density increase with increase in concentration and temperature. At high surfactant concentration, the number density of micelles is high and therefore the distance between them decrease⁹. The viscosity increases with increase in concentration. When the concentration of the surfactant is low, the viscosity of solutions is also low, which makes the measurement and analysis more difficult.

Adiabatic compressibility (β) and intermolecular free

Table 1. Acoustic parameters of aqueous 0.3 mM (DTAC) with various (PEO) at 303 K and 323 K temperatures

PEO conc. (mM)	Ultrasonic velocity (<i>U</i>) (m/s)		Density (ρ) (kg/m ³)		Viscosity (η) (Ns m ⁻²)		Adiabatic compressibility (β) (kg/ms ²) × 10 ¹⁰		Free length (<i>L_f</i>) (Å)		Internal pressure (π _i) × 10 ⁻⁶ Pascal		Acoustic impedance (<i>Z_a</i>) × 10 ⁶ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	
	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K
	0.3	1509	1516	1004	1019	4.432	5.232	4.374	4.270	0.417	0.412	183	213	1.515
0.6	1513	1519	1009	1021	4.664	5.414	4.329	4.244	0.415	0.411	170	196	1.526	1.550
0.9	1517	1522	1011	1024	4.856	5.637	4.298	4.215	0.413	0.409	166	192	1.533	1.558
1.2	1521	1528	1015	1027	5.137	5.872	4.258	4.170	0.411	0.407	163	192	1.543	1.569
1.5	1516	1523	1018	1030	5.323	5.934	4.274	4.185	0.412	0.408	162	191	1.543	1.568

Table 2. Acoustic parameters of aqueous 0.3 mM (DTAC) with various (PPO) at 303 K and 323 K temperatures

PEO conc. (mM)	Ultrasonic velocity (<i>U</i>) (m/s)		Density (ρ) (kg/m ³)		Viscosity (η) (Ns m ⁻²)		Adiabatic compressibility (β) (kg/ms ²) × 10 ¹⁰		Free length (<i>L_f</i>) (Å)		Internal pressure (π _i) × 10 ⁻⁶ Pascal		Acoustic impedance (<i>Z_a</i>) × 10 ⁶ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	
	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K
	0.3	1504	1511	998	1007	4.033	4.421	4.429	4.349	0.419	0.416	175	195	1.500
0.6	1506	1513	1001	1011	4.346	4.632	4.404	4.320	0.418	0.414	164	180	1.507	1.529
0.9	1510	1516	1003	1015	4.557	4.801	4.372	4.286	0.417	0.413	161	177	1.514	1.538
1.2	1514	1521	1005	1019	4.716	4.968	4.340	4.241	0.415	0.410	160	176	1.521	1.549
1.5	1511	1518	1008	1021	4.831	5.123	4.345	4.250	0.415	0.411	161	177	1.523	1.549

Table 3. Acoustic parameters of aqueous 0.3 mM (DTAC) with various (PBO) at 303 K and 323 K temperatures

PEO conc. (mM)	Ultrasonic velocity (U) (m/s)		Density (ρ) (kg/m ³)		Viscosity (η) (Ns m ⁻²)		Adiabatic compressibility (β) (kg/ms ²) $\times 10^{10}$		Free length (L_f) (Å)		Internal pressure (π_i) $\times 10^{-6}$ Pascal		Acoustic impedance (Z_a) $\times 10^6$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	
	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K	303 K	323 K
	0.3	1496	1501	992	995	4.010	4.286	4.504	4.460	0.423	0.421	174	192	1.484
0.6	1499	1504	996	998	4.137	4.431	4.468	4.290	0.421	0.419	160	176	1.493	1.500
0.9	1502	1507	999	1002	4.310	4.642	4.437	4.394	0.420	0.418	157	173	1.500	1.510
1.2	1505	1511	1002	1006	4.481	4.822	4.406	4.353	0.418	0.416	157	173	1.508	1.520
1.5	1502	1508	1005	1111	4.621	4.951	4.410	3.958	0.419	0.395	158	175	1.509	1.675

length decreases up to CMC and then a slight increase is observed. It may be explained on the basis of close-packing of ionic head groups in the micelles resulting in an increase in ionic repulsion and finally internal pressure. When the size of the surfactant chain increases the repulsion also increase, thereby a decrease in the value of adiabatic compressibility (β) occurs. The decrease in β is attributed to the fact that the surfactant molecules are surrounded by a layer of solvent molecules¹⁰.

Intermolecular free length depends upon the adiabatic compressibility and shows a behavior inversely related to the velocity. The behavior of intermolecular free length is an inverse behavior of sound propagation.

The variation of ultrasonic velocity in a solution depends on the intermolecular free length (L_f). Ultrasonic velocity (U) increases with decreasing L_f and vice versa. In the present case, L_f decreases linearly with increasing velocity, concentration and temperature. This indicates the significant surfactant-polymer interaction suggesting a structure promoting the solute-solvent interaction. This is further supported by an increase in acoustical impedance (Z_a) and decrease in internal pressure (π_i), compressibility with increasing concentration and temperature.

The specific acoustic impedance (Z_a) increases with increase in concentration of DTAC/PEO, DTAC/PPO and DTAC/PBO aqueous solutions (Tables 1 to 3). Based on the lyophobic interaction, increase in the value of Z_a with increase in polymer concentration can be elucidated. The intermolecular distances leave a relatively wider gap between the molecules and thus becoming the main cause of impediment to the propagation of ultrasonic waves.

Conclusion

The present study observing the ultrasonic velocity and other acoustical data of the surfactant and polymers in water show hydrogen bonding interaction between the solute and solvent molecules. When the concentration of polymer exceeds the surfactant saturation point (PSP), the micellar concentration become critical. At any given concentration, the increasing order of velocity is PEO > PPO > PBO. This observation strengthens the structural interactions in promoting the hydrogen-bonded structure of water. The increases in mass due to the alkene chain influence the intermolecular interaction and bring down the H-bonding strength.

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